

Factsheet¹

Messages from
the summary for policymakers

The Thematic Assessment of **THE INTERLINKAGES AMONG BIODIVERSITY, WATER, FOOD AND HEALTH** (Nexus Assessment)²

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1 / Climate change and nexus approaches³

Overview

Biodiversity loss and climate change are interdependent and produce compounding impacts {KM-A1}. Climate change has important and increasing, yet often overlooked, interactions with biodiversity, water, food and health, the so-called nexus elements. Climate change is a key direct driver of biodiversity loss. Climate change affects biodiversity, water, food and health, and these nexus elements also influence climate change {BM-A5}.⁴

Nexus approaches are crucial because, despite the intertwined nature of the drivers and underlying causes of degradation of biodiversity, water, food, health and climate, decisions to address them are often taken in isolation, resulting in potential misalignment, unplanned trade-offs and/or unintended consequences. Transforming current siloed modes of governance enables successful implementation of response options to manage the nexus elements in an integrated manner, with benefits for people and nature now and into the future {KM-D1}.

Nexus-wide benefits depend on reducing climate change and ensuring that climate change mitigation approaches do not negatively impact other nexus elements {KM-B1}.

1. This factsheet is part of a series of factsheets, which highlight a selection of key elements on specific themes from the Summary for Policymakers of the IPBES Nexus Assessment. For further information and context, please consult the Summary for Policymakers and Chapters of that Assessment Report.
2. IPBES (2024). Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Interlinkages among Biodiversity, Water, Food and Health of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. McElwee, P. D., Harrison, P. A., van Huysen, T. L., Alonso Roldán, V., Barrios, E., Dasgupta, P., DeClerck, F., Harmáčková, Z. V., Hayman, D. T. S., Herrero, M., Kumar, R., Ley, D., Mangalagiu, D., McFarlane, R. A., Paukert, C., Pengue, W. A., Prist, P. R., Ricketts, T. H., Rounsevell, M. D. A., Saito, O., Selomane, O., Seppelt, R., Singh, P. K., Sitas, N., Smith, P., Vause, J., Molua, E. L., Zambrana-Torrel, C., and Obura, D. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13850289>
3. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.20425323>
4. The references enclosed in curly brackets (e.g., {KM-C1, B11}) are traceable accounts and refer to sections of the Summary for Policymakers. A traceable account is a guide to the section in the summary for policymakers and the chapters that contains the evidence supporting a given message and reflecting the evaluation of the type, amount, quality and consistency of evidence and the degree of agreement for that statement or key finding.

Climate change is inextricably linked to biodiversity and other nexus elements

Global trends in indirect drivers — including economic, demographic, cultural and technological change (such as overconsumption and waste)— have intensified direct drivers of biodiversity loss (land- and sea-use change, unsustainable exploitation, pollution, invasive alien species and climate change), with cascading effects on all nexus elements (*well established*) {BM-A1, 2.3.1, 2.3.2, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6.1}. Ten out of twelve indicators of indirect drivers have increased since 2001 (*established but incomplete*) {BM-A1, 2.3.2}.

Climate change affects biodiversity, water, food and health through changes in average climatic conditions and in the frequency and magnitude of extreme weather events (*well established*) {BM-A5, 2.5.2.2}.

- ▶ In the past 50 years, extreme weather-, climate- and water-related events caused nearly 12,000 disasters, leading to 2 million human deaths (90% in low- and lower-middle-income countries) and \$4.3 trillion in costs globally (*well established*) {BM-A5, 2.5}.
- ▶ 58% (218 out of 375) of known human infectious diseases are likely to worsen owing to climate change (*established but incomplete*) {BM-A5, 2.5.2.2}.
- ▶ Climate change has slowed growth in agricultural productivity and has negative effects on coastal fisheries and marine food systems that prevent malnutrition, including for the nearly one billion people living within 100 km of coral reefs (*well established*) {BM-A3, BM-A2, 2.4.1, 2.4.4, 2.5.2}.

Biodiversity, water, food, health and climate change are interconnected, and biodiversity loss due to climate change can amplify negative feedback loops (*well established*) {2.5.2.2}:

- ▶ Land-use change associated with food production was responsible for an estimated 21% of global carbon dioxide equivalent emissions in 2018 (*well established*) {BM-A5, 2.5.2.1, 5.3.1}.
- ▶ Biodiversity loss reduces the ability of ecosystems, such as forests and oceans, to sequester carbon, thereby increasing greenhouse gas concentrations and accelerating climate change itself (*well established*) {KM-A1, BM-A5, 5.5.3}.
- ▶ Wetlands and inland water bodies — covering just 2.6% of Earth's terrestrial surface — play a significant role in water regulation and climate mitigation and adaptation; a substantial proportion have been degraded or lost over past centuries (*well established*) {BM-A2, 2.3.3, 2.5.1}.

The impacts of climate change are unequally distributed (*well established*) {BM-A7, 2.5.3.1}.

- ▶ More than half the world's population is living in areas experiencing the highest impacts from declines in biodiversity, water availability and quality, food security, and from increases in health risks and negative effects of climate change. These burdens disproportionately affect developing countries, including small island developing States, Indigenous Peoples and local communities, as well as those in vulnerable situations in higher-income countries {KM-A3}.

Temporal trends in climate-related disasters {2.3.3}

Siloed climate action is insufficient — and costly

Exposure to risks from climate change is projected to double in the case of warming levels between 1.5°C and 2°C (*well established*) and double again between 2°C and 3°C (*established but incomplete*), stressing water resources, food systems, biodiversity and human health {BM-B4, 3.6.2}.

Future scenarios with positive outcomes across all nexus elements are characterized by timely adoption

of sustainable consumption and production practices, enhanced climate change mitigation and adaptation action, and considerations of multiple values and knowledge systems (*established but incomplete*) {KM-B1, 3.7.1, 3.7.3} (see [Figure SPM.5](#)). However, scenarios that prioritize objectives for a single element of the nexus will result in trade-offs across the nexus {KM-B1}.

A climate first scenario approach could lead to additional negative outcomes for biodiversity and food as a result of primarily prioritizing climate change mitigation actions (*well established*) {BM-B4, 3.6.3, 3.7.1}.

In contrast, scenarios that are characterized by integrated climate actions such as conserving and restoring ecosystems for carbon sequestration have nexus-wide benefits (*well established*) {BM-B4, 3.6.3, 3.7.1, 3.7.2}.

Delaying action to meet climate goals could increase the costs of adaptation and mitigation by a minimum of approximately \$500 billion per year, while delaying action on biodiversity

policy goals could double the eventual costs of action (*established but incomplete*) {KM-B1, KM-B5, 6.1.2.4, 7.2.4, 7.2.5}.

Negative externalities (costs not considered as part of decision-making processes) across the fossil fuel, agriculture and fisheries sectors are currently estimated at \$10–25 trillion per year, while expenditures to improve the status of nature amount to less than 1% of global GDP (*established but incomplete*) {BM-A6, 6.1.3, 6.2.2, 6.2.3, 7.2.3}. Additional investment needs to meet the Sustainable Development Goals most directly related to water, food, health and climate change are at least \$4 trillion per year {KM-D2}.

Numerous response options deliver synergistic climate and nexus benefits

Seventy-one response options were assessed across 10 broad categories (see overleaf). Some deliver benefits across all nexus elements simultaneously, including for climate change mitigation and adaptation. Response options, when implemented at appropriate scales and contexts, provide many benefits to different degrees across the nexus elements, and many are low cost {KM-C1}. Key response options with strong climate co-benefits include:

- ▶ **Conserving or halting the conversion of forests and other ecosystems** protects human health and well-being by combating climate change, reducing the impact of extreme weather events and reducing disease risk (*well established*) {BM-C1, 5.4.3.8, 5.5.3.10}.
- ▶ **Restoring natural and semi-natural ecosystems** — including forests, peatlands, wetlands, seagrass beds, salt marshes and mangroves — contributes to both climate change mitigation (through carbon sequestration) and adaptation (through socio-ecological resilience) (*well established*) {BM-C2, 5.5.3.4, 5.5.3.12, 5.5.3.13}.
- ▶ **Shifting to sustainable consumption patterns and renewable energy** (e.g., offshore wind energy) helps to mitigate

climate change (*well established*) {5.5.1}, but environmental assessments and appropriate policies would be needed to avoid trade-offs, particularly for biodiversity and food systems (*well established*) {BM-C4, 5.5.3.5, 5.5.3.6}.

- ▶ **Effective risk management** — including early warning systems and urban nature-based solutions — reduces climate and health risks, particularly where these are multi-scale and interlinked (*well established*) {BM-C7, 5.5.3.9}.
- ▶ **Ensuring rights and equity** — such as through Indigenous food systems — can supply sustainable, healthy foods while contributing to climate change mitigation and adaptation (*well established*) {BM-C8, 5.3.3}.

Response options can strongly advance global policy efforts, including the Sustainable Development Goals, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and the Paris Agreement (*well established*) {KM-C3}.

However, many response options will be less effective or impossible to implement if climate change is not urgently addressed (*well established*) {BM-C10, 2.5.2.2, 3.6.2}.

Nexus governance is needed to address climate change and other challenges together

Climate change mitigation policies are more effective in future scenarios that minimize trade-offs across the nexus elements, such as planning actions in an integrated way to avoid competition for land and other resources between climate change mitigation actions and the other nexus elements {KM-B3}. Siloed policy approaches and actions that prioritize a single nexus element limit the achievement of benefits across policy goals {KM-B3, KM-B5}.

Transforming current siloed modes of governance through more integrative, inclusive, equitable, accountable, coordinated and adaptive approaches enables successful implementation of response options to manage the nexus elements, and their associated direct and indirect drivers, in an integrated manner,

with benefits for people and nature now and into the future {KM-D1, BM-A1, BM-A7, BM-D1, BM-D2}.

Reforms to governance and economic systems can be facilitated by deliberate steps to identify existing challenges and contexts, increase actor engagement through coordination, knowledge co-production and strategic action and seek iterative, adaptive and scalable solutions (*established but incomplete*) {BM-D4, 4.5, 5.6, 6.2, 7.3}. For example, actors involved in subnational, national, regional or transboundary development planning processes could use steps of the road map (see Figure SPM.13), where relevant, when co-developing national biodiversity strategies and action plans, nationally determined contributions and national adaptation plans {BM-D4}.

Response options have substantial but varying impacts on climate

For each of the response options assessed in Chapter 5, circles indicate the estimated impacts on climate change (both adaptation and mitigation). Larger circles indicate stronger impacts. Most impacts are positive (blue), but a few response options have negative impacts (red). Unique alphanumeric codes for each response option indicate its nexus element (B for biodiversity, W for water, F for food, H for health and C for climate change) and its corresponding number in the relevant subchapter of Chapter 5. Impact scores are based on a thorough review of existing evidence, synthesized and averaged across several component criteria (greenhouse gas emissions reduction/carbon sequestration potential and adaptation impact) on a scale of -3 to +3 {5.0}. Response options for which evidence for component indicators was inconclusive (IC) or non-existent (NE) are labelled as such. Response options with an * were each assessed in two different subchapters and both alphanumeric codes are shown. For more details, see Figure SPM.8 in the Nexus Assessment.